

THERMAL VISCOELASTIC ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE CYLINDERS OF THERMORHEOLOGICALLY SIMPLE CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The linear quasi-static thermal viscoelastic behavior of a thick-walled laminated composite cylinder with an elevated temperature change is studied in the present research. The correspondence principle is applied on this thermorheologically simple material for the Laplace transformed solution which is resulted from a closed form formulation of each individual layer. Using the normal continuity conditions between adjacent layers and employing the direct Laplace inverse transformation method, the time dependent viscoelastic result is obtained. Furthermore, the radial displacement profiles and all nonvanished stress profiles across the thickness of the cylinder at three time states are shown.

1. INTRODUCTION

Various mathematical formulations derived from thermodynamics postulates to characterize the viscoelastic behavior for isotropic materials can be found in earlier studies¹⁻⁵. These basic theories of viscoelasticity were then extended to the area of heterogeneous and anisotropic materials for a variety of applications. Yet, not much research literature has been seen in the area of thick-walled viscoelastic cylindrical composites. The thick laminated composite cylinders are of particular interest to the Army's weapons technology research for potential ballistic applications. Thus, the imminent need for investigating the viscoelastic behavior of thick laminated composite cylinders is becoming prominent.

In the following research, the linear quasi-static viscoelastic behavior of a three-dimensional thick-walled laminated composite cylinder with an elevated temperature change is studied. The thick-walled cylinder is assumed in the state of generalized plane strain such that all the stress and strain components are independent of axial coordinate. Moreover, due to the nature of axisymmetry, all the stress and strain components are also independent of the circumferential coordinate. The mechanical responses of this thick-walled composite cylinder will, therefore, only have to satisfy the governing equation in the radial direction. Invoking the Boltzmann superposition integral for the complete spectrum of increments of anisotropic material constants with respect to time, the thermal viscoelastic constitutive relations of

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the anisotropic composite cylinder can be derived in integral forms. Since the thick-walled composite cylinder is subjected to a constant elevated temperature change and boundary conditions are all independent of time, formulations of the linear thermal viscoelastic problem can have forms identical to those of the corresponding linear thermoelastic problem by taking advantage of the elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle. In other words, all of these integral constitutive equations reduce to the algebraic relations, which are very similar to those developed for thermoelastic media when they are Laplace transformed by means of the rule for convolution integrals. The thermoelastic analysis can thus be used to derive the transformed thermal viscoelastic solutions in the frequency domain.

Following these treatments, the general analytical viscoelastic solution in the frequency domain for each layer is obtained in the form of the corresponding thermoelastic solution. The analytical solution accounts for the ply-by-ply variation of material properties, fiber orientation, and the uniform temperature change through the thickness of the cylinder. Further, the general analytical solution for the corresponding thermoelastic boundary value problem is completed by satisfying the boundary conditions and continuity conditions between adjacent layers. The boundary conditions require the tractions to be free on both inner and outer circular surfaces and two ends. The continuity conditions at the interfaces between two adjacent layers, under the assumption of generalized plane strain, lead to two nontrivial continuity conditions, i.e., normal traction continuity and normal displacement continuity. As a result, solving a system of $2N$ (where N is the number of the composite cylinder layers) simultaneous equations is needed for the analytical solution of each individual layer as well as the cylinder as a whole. A technique of replacing two undetermined coefficients in the solution by the normal stresses at inner and outer surfaces of each layer and applying the normal continuity conditions is then employed to solve the resulting smaller system of $N + 1$ equations. The Laplace transformed thermal viscoelastic solution is thus obtained by properly substituting the transformed mechanical constants into the corresponding thermoelastic solution. Finally, the direct Laplace inverse transformation method is incorporated to yield the time dependent result.

2. GENERAL FORMULATION

Consider a filament-wound axisymmetric thick laminated composite cylinder consisting of N layers with the axial coordinate z , the radial coordinate r , and the circumferential coordinate θ , as shown in Figure 1. This composite cylinder has the inner radius a , the outer radius b , and the length L . The Boltzmann superposition integral of linear anisotropic stress σ_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) and strain ϵ_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) relation for an isothermal viscoelastic problem with a constant elevated temperature ΔT and the thermal expansion coefficient α_{kl} is

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = \int_0^t C_{ij}^{kl}(T, t - \tau) \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kl}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \beta_{ij}(T, t) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where $C_{ij}^{kl}(T, t)$ is the relaxation modulus dependent on temperature T and time t , and $\beta_{ij}(T, t)$ can be characterized as $\beta_{ij}(T, t) = C_{ij}^{kl}(T, t) \cdot \alpha_{kl}$. Since the elevated temperature change ΔT is constant above some reference value in time, the relaxation moduli and creep compliances are evaluated at that reference value of temperature regardless of employing temperature shift-factor and whether or not the material is thermorheologically simple.

The Laplace transform of a function $f(t)$ is known as

$$\bar{f} = \bar{f}(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt \quad (2)$$

where s is the Laplace transform variable. Applying (2) with the convolution rule on (1), the anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive equations become the following algebraic relation

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \tilde{C}_{ij}^{kl} \bar{\epsilon}_{kl} - \tilde{\beta}_{ij} \frac{\Delta T}{s} \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^{kl} = s\bar{C}_{ij}^{kl}$, $\tilde{\alpha}_{ij} = s\bar{\alpha}_{ij}$, and $\tilde{\beta}_{kl} = \tilde{C}_{ij}^{kl} \cdot \tilde{\alpha}_{ij}$.

The transformed axisymmetric displacement field gives the transformed strain components in cylindrical coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon}_{rr} &= \frac{d\bar{w}(r)}{dr}, \quad \bar{\epsilon}_{\theta\theta} = \frac{\bar{w}(r)}{r} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} &= \frac{d\bar{u}}{dz} = \bar{\epsilon}^o, \quad \bar{\epsilon}_{\theta r} = \bar{\epsilon}_{zr} = \bar{\epsilon}_{z\theta} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, it can be shown that two of the three equilibrium equations are satisfied automatically. The only nontrivial equilibrium equation is in the radial direction

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{rr}}{\partial r} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{rr} - \bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Substituting (4) into (3), the transformed stress components $\bar{\sigma}_{rr}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}$ are obtained in terms of the transformed radial displacement \bar{w} . Incorporating the resulting $\bar{\sigma}_{rr}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}$ functions with (5) gives a nonhomogeneous Euler differential equation of \bar{w} for a layer

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 \bar{w}}{dr^2} + r \frac{d\bar{w}}{dr} - \tilde{\lambda}^2 \bar{w} = \frac{r}{\tilde{C}_{33}} \left[\frac{\Delta T}{s} (\tilde{\beta}_{rr} - \tilde{\beta}_{\theta\theta}) - (\tilde{C}_{13} - \tilde{C}_{12}) \bar{\epsilon}^o \right] \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{\lambda}^2 = \frac{\tilde{C}_{22}}{\tilde{C}_{33}} \quad (7)$$

Solving (6) for \bar{w} yields

$$\bar{w} = \bar{A}_1 r^{\tilde{\lambda}} + \bar{A}_2 r^{-\tilde{\lambda}} + \tilde{w}_p \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{w}_p &= \tilde{f}_1 \bar{\epsilon}^o r + \tilde{f}_3 r \\ \tilde{f}_1 &= \frac{\tilde{C}_{12} - \tilde{C}_{13}}{\tilde{C}_{33} - \tilde{C}_{22}} \\ \tilde{f}_3 &= \frac{\tilde{S}}{\tilde{C}_{33} - \tilde{C}_{22}} \\ \tilde{S} &= \frac{\Delta T}{s} [\tilde{\beta}_{rr} - \tilde{\beta}_{\theta\theta}] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

and \bar{A}_1 and \bar{A}_2 are coefficients to be determined from boundary and continuity conditions.

The continuity conditions at each interface between two adjacent layers require continuous radial traction and continuous radial displacement at any instant. When written in the transformed form, they become

$$\bar{\sigma}_{rr,o}^{(k)} - \bar{\sigma}_{rr,i}^{(k+1)} = 0 \quad (10)$$

and

$$\bar{w}_{,o}^{(k)} = \bar{w}_{,i}^{(k+1)} \quad (11)$$

where $k = 1, \dots, N-1$; and $\square_{,i}$ and $\square_{,o}$ denote the quantity \square that is evaluated at inner and outer surfaces, respectively.

Assembling the \bar{w} ply by ply and incorporating the continuity conditions (10) and (11) give the global system of equations of \bar{w}

$$\begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{a}_{11}^{(1)} & \bar{a}_{12}^{(1)} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{a}_{21}^{(1)} & \bar{a}_{22}^{(1)} - \bar{a}_{11}^{(2)} & \bar{a}_{12}^{(2)} & 0 & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \bar{a}_{21}^{(2)} & \bar{a}_{22}^{(2)} - \bar{a}_{11}^{(3)} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & \vdots & \ddots & \bar{a}_{12}^{(N-1)} & 0 \\ 0 & \vdots & 0 & 0 & \bar{a}_{22}^{(N-1)} - \bar{a}_{11}^{(N)} & \bar{a}_{12}^{(N)} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{a}_{21}^{(N)} & \bar{a}_{22}^{(N)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{w}_{,i}^{(1)} \\ \bar{w}_{,i}^{(2)} \\ \bar{w}_{,i}^{(3)} \\ \vdots \\ \bar{w}_{,i}^{(N)} \\ \bar{w}_{,o}^{(N)} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{f}_1^{(1)} \\ \bar{f}_2^{(1)} - \bar{f}_1^{(2)} \\ \bar{f}_2^{(2)} - \bar{f}_1^{(3)} \\ \vdots \\ \bar{f}_2^{(N-1)} - \bar{f}_1^{(N)} \\ \bar{f}_2^{(N)} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where $\square^{(k)}$ indicates the quantity \square for the layer k , the coefficient matrix of each layer

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{a}_{11} & \bar{a}_{12} \\ \bar{a}_{21} & \bar{a}_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 r_i^{\lambda-1} & b_2 r_i^{-\lambda-1} \\ b_1 r_o^{\lambda-1} & b_2 r_o^{-\lambda-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_i^{\lambda} & r_i^{-\lambda} \\ r_o^{\lambda} & r_o^{-\lambda} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

the forcing function induced by ΔT of each layer

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{f}_1(\Delta T) \\ \bar{f}_2(\Delta T) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} c_2 \\ c_2 \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} b_1 r_i^{\lambda-1} & b_2 r_i^{-\lambda-1} \\ b_1 r_o^{\lambda-1} & b_2 r_o^{-\lambda-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_i^{\lambda} & r_i^{-\lambda} \\ r_o^{\lambda} & r_o^{-\lambda} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} c_1 r_i \\ c_1 r_o \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \tilde{C}_{33} \tilde{\lambda} + \tilde{C}_{23} \\ b_2 &= -\tilde{C}_{33} \tilde{\lambda} + \tilde{C}_{23} \\ c_1 &= \tilde{f}_1 \bar{\epsilon}^\circ + \tilde{f}_3 \\ c_2 &= (\tilde{C}_{33} + \tilde{C}_{23}) c_1 + \tilde{C}_{13} \bar{\epsilon}^\circ - \frac{\Delta T}{s} \tilde{\beta}_{rr} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The transformed axial strain $\bar{\epsilon}^\circ$ is obtained as following by applying the $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$ into the end free boundary conditions.

$$\bar{\epsilon}^\circ = - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N [P_1^k + P_2^k + P_3^k]}{\sum_{k=1}^N Q^k} \quad (16)$$

where

$$Q^k = \tilde{C}_{11} t_1 + \tilde{C}_{12} \tilde{f}_1 t_1 + \tilde{C}_{13} \tilde{f}_1 t_1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_1^k &= (\tilde{C}_{12}t_2 + \tilde{C}_{13}\tilde{\lambda}t_2)\bar{A}_1 \\
P_2^k &= (\tilde{C}_{12}t_3 - \tilde{C}_{13}\tilde{\lambda}t_3)\bar{A}_2 \\
P_3^k &= \tilde{C}_{12}\tilde{f}_3t_1 + \tilde{C}_{13}\tilde{f}_3t_1 - \frac{\Delta T}{s}\tilde{\beta}_{zz}t_1 \\
t_1 &= \int_{r_i}^{r_o} r dr = \frac{1}{2}(r_o^2 - r_i^2) \\
t_2 &= \int_{r_i}^{r_o} r^{\tilde{\lambda}} dr = \frac{1}{\tilde{\lambda} + 1}(r_o^{\tilde{\lambda}+1} - r_i^{\tilde{\lambda}+1}) \\
t_3 &= \int_{r_i}^{r_o} r^{-\tilde{\lambda}} dr = \frac{1}{-\tilde{\lambda} + 1}(r_o^{-\tilde{\lambda}+1} - r_i^{-\tilde{\lambda}+1})
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

The forcing function (14) is in terms of c_1 and c_2 , which are all functions of $\bar{\epsilon}^o$. Further, to complete the result of $\bar{\epsilon}^o$ (16) requires finding the solution of \bar{A}_1 and \bar{A}_2 of each layer. Completing the results of \bar{w} 's (12) and the $\bar{\epsilon}^o$ (16) thus indicates that the global system of equations of \bar{w} 's (12) and the $\bar{\epsilon}^o$ (16) form a set of two coupled nonlinear equations. The Newton-Raphson iteration technique is utilized herein for the final solution of \bar{w} 's.

Finally, the direct Laplace inverse transformation method

$$f(t) \simeq \left[s\bar{f}(s) \right]_{s=\frac{1}{t}} \tag{18}$$

is employed to provide the time dependent viscoelastic solution.

3. ILLUSTRATED PROBLEM

The time dependent thermal viscoelastic behavior of a 100-layer AS-4/3502 graphite epoxy thick-walled laminated composite cylinder subjected to an elevated temperature change $\Delta T = 150^\circ C$ is examined. The composite cylinder has an inner radius $a = 3.5$ inches, an outer radius $b = 4.1$ inches, and a thickness of each layer $h = 6.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ inches. Stacking sequence is characterized as $[0/30/60/90]_{25}$ from inside out with the 0° line of a lamina coinciding with the axial line of the cylinder. The creep mechanical properties of AS-4/3502 graphite epoxy at $\Delta T = 150^\circ C$ were shown previously⁶.

The viscoelastic responses at three time states $t = 10^{-3} min.$, $t = 10^{4.5} min.$ and $t = 10^{12} min.$ are demonstrated in the present study. Figure 2 presents the radial displacement profiles across the thickness of the cylinder at the three time states. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the hoop stress profiles and axial stress profiles, respectively across the thickness of the cylinder at the three time states. Due to the limited space available, the detailed discussion will be given later.

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Figure 1. Cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) of an axisymmetric thick laminated composite cylinder containing N layers with the inner radius a , the outer radius b , and the length L .

Figure 2. Radial displacement profiles across the thickness of the cylinder at three time states $t = 10^{-3} \text{ min.}$, $t = 10^{4.5} \text{ min.}$ and $t = 10^{12} \text{ min.}$.

Figure 3. Hoop stress profiles across the thickness of the cylinder at three time states $t = 10^{-3} \text{ min.}$ $t = 10^{4.5} \text{ min.}$ and $t = 10^{12} \text{ min.}$

Figure 4. Axial stress profiles across the thickness of the cylinder at three time states $t = 10^{-3} \text{ min.}$, $t = 10^{4.5} \text{ min.}$, and $t = 10^{12} \text{ min.}$.